

Towards a Global Market Domination under a Linguistic and a Sociocultural Soft Power Strategy

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Abstract

This research seeks to investigate the domination on the local markets worldwide by highlighting the soft power strategy use, as came in Nye's concept (2008). Furthermore, it studies the impact of localisation and transcreation to provide a baseline understanding of how products and advertisements are introduced to the target audience. This study examines, under a qualitative approach, exclusive advertisement figures that carry geo-cultural conceptions and under a geo-marketing strategy. The findings led to significant demonstrations that offered remarkable variables, because they were strongly related to going global by acting local policy and in each case, the adopted strategy was unique. The current study contributes theoretically in presenting transcreation technique for following linguistic and sociocultural guidelines of the target expression in order to better address the target audience. Moreover, this study contributes practically in demonstrating some implications that identify the target expression and the target audience alike. This study is one of the very few that touches upon the multidisciplinary approaches where geo-political, geo-economical and geo-cultural features are incorporated in shaping identities of the world's order. It also contributes to the understanding of the theorisation and the practicality of powers that are shaping minds and decisions, eventually.

Keywords: geo-approaches; soft power; domination; local markets; transcreation; advertisements.

1. Introduction

Any given geographical area, almost anywhere in this planet, is not an unidentifiable space but a territory that has borderlines, set of rules and norms that are determined by the governors and the locals. This group of people are gathered and unified under their own distinctive identity. Politics, economy, society, culture, language and so on and so forth represent the rules and the norms that this group of people are following and eventually are identified with. These patterns are what create the differences among people across the globe. Rules and norms appear to be distinctive in each country. Moreover, the accumulation of historical events and their evolutions throughout time and the people's flexibility in adopting new ways of managing their living in the contemporary world represent also the identity features of this group of people, composed of citizens and rulers. But despite the dissimilarity among the groups, it is very important to keep the link that connects these different communities with their near and far neighbours worldwide. This relation of connectivity is very important, on so many levels. It is indeed for the growth and the development of these nations. Some countries even moved to the next level with their relations, where many countries formulated a union that added more value and power to their identity such as the European Union, or the so called transnational relations. Others preferred to disjoin the group such as the Brexit. So, whether it is a union or a parting, they both regulate relations.

Geo-approaches (the geo-politics, the geo-economics and the geo-cultures) are basically the geo-strategies that regulate the relations with the locals, the representatives of the country and the foreigners.

Rozov clarifies this situation as follows: “discussions about international relations are conducted in the terms of geopolitics (security, strength, conflicts, coalitions) [...], geo-economics (growth, development trade, investment,

dependence, and others) [... and] geo-culture [...] (prestige, exchange, cultural influence, similarity or difference in religious faiths). Everyone realizes that these spheres are closely interconnected”.¹

Therefore, knowing and taking these approaches into consideration may determine how relations on the transnational or the transcultural level are managed. In this investigation, more light, in particular, will be shed on the economical relations between global companies and their domination on new local markets worldwide, where their marketing strategy is softly powerful. The reason behind is that they use local linguistic and sociocultural aspects as their means of communication with their new local clients via transcreated advertisements.

So from the economical perspectives and for the marketing strategies, the local aspects impact should be studied and used on the favour of the global market investors, when they aim at widening their commercialisation operation and gain more local markets abroad. Schlegelmilch thinks that the locals' preferences in their purchases are related to their local rules and norms, because it is very hard to manage creating a global segment with global standards. As a matter of fact, there has to be some adjustments in the product, the service or even the way advertisements are presented to the new customers in order to fit more the local standards.

Schlegelmilch explicitly says that: “There are opportunities for marketers to pursue some segments on a global scale. However, the predicted global uniformity finds its limits in language differences, national laws and a large variety of cultural factors. Companies with a wide global reach still encounter a large number of regional and national preferences that limit the scope for truly global segments”.²

It is then recommended to make some changes on the marketing strategy as on the advertisements conceptions, to reach the targeted audience, efficiently. The geo-approaches are identified with one common element: the geographical

sphere. But it is also what imposes the difference in each territory. For more in depth clarification regarding the three geo-approaches impact on the economical transactions and relations, they are all discussed as follows:

- Geo-politics represent the hard power of the country. It is then a set of rules, applied on a specific territory.

Cowen and Smith says: “Geopolitics embodies a range of assumptions that entwine political power to the territorially demarcated system of national states, and it reads national cultures, societies and economies as more or less aligned to those territorial divisions of the world”.³

In other words, the major approach that regulates the relations is the geopolitics because it is the determiner of the form of the power the state exercises on different kinds of relations between the other approaches, such as the geo-economical and the geo-cultural ones. Therefore, if new local markets are targeted in order to display global products and services for commercialisation purposes, the marketing strategy should go for a mass commercialisation and under the geopolitics regulations, as for creating flexible strategies that do not break the local rules.

- Geo-marketing represents the undertaken strategy to win or dominate both the domestic and the global markets.

Cowen and Smith see that: “the transition to a globalized geo-economic world is not a matter of some natural evolution in economic affairs, but a case of active assembly, albeit fomented by very real scalar shifts in economic relations”.⁴

The situation here is very clear. If settling on new local markets abroad, the marketing strategy goes with a lot of effort to be done in order to make of this new commercial horizon a welcoming one. The shifts in economic relations are very crucial because the facts and the statistics provide different data of the new market. Starting from different languages, different target audience of clients and different policies... etc, they all then require active planning and changes

that adapt the product and service or the advertisement to the new client of the new local market.

The expansion of the marketing strategy is also called the macro-marketing. But the micro-marketing is applied on niche markets. Regarding these strategies, Schlegelmilch sees that:

“Mass marketing [...] Here, a company targets the entire market, disregarding differences among market segments and concentrating on their commonalities. [...] Other approaches are known as niche or concentrated marketing, where a company attempts to capture a large proportion of one or a few smaller market segments of niches. Companies pursuing such strategies usually obtain a high degree of market knowledge through this concentrated strategy”.⁵

Selling for the global market requires relatively common standards of commercialisation. But when aiming for selling to a specific type of clients, at this level, more studies and investigations are conducted in order to understand and cover the need of this niche market. As a matter of fact, it is obvious that neither the demand nor the offer should be standardised. It is rather a set of customisations that are applied on the new local market offers to the target clients' demands.

- Geo-culture represents the soft power. It is manifested in the language, local thinking, habits, traditions...etc. It is obvious that cultures vary from region to region. Showing much appreciation and respect to the local culture can only be one of the strongest arsenals that can be used to link the identity of the productive company to the cultural identity of the targeted geo-culture.

Winter sees that: “*Geocultural Power* thus explores the strategy of coaching trade and political relations, energy and political security, in an evocative topography of history”.⁶

It is with no doubt, that the soft power is way more powerful than the hard power because it coaches many relations, smoothly. It makes people's resistance

or repulsion very lower in the commercialisation strategy. At this stage, translation intervenes in order to bridge the two different cultures. On this purpose, advertisements for instance are being translated to the local language. But if translation only seems impossible to be done, the transcreation technique, which is a concept beyond the services of the direct translation, takes place in order to transfer not just the linguistic content of the advertisement, but also to incorporate features of the local culture in the conception of the advertisement to be presented to the new target client. On top of that, it is very possible to create a positive impact and influence on the new client because transcreation works on translating and creating the advertising contents under the fitting measurements to the target market, target client and target culture. Therefore, the language, the culture and the impact become all combined in one conception that serves the positive reception of the transcreated advertisement in the new geo-cultural sphere.

For the commercialisation purposes, the connection of the three geo-approaches: geo-politics, geo-marketing and geo-culture serve all the marketing strategy that should be different if evolving from winning the domestic markets at home country to gaining more new markets abroad. It is actually called the globalisation strategy. The foreign language, foreign culture and foreign society rules may be regarded as obstacles in reaching the target audience's minds and hearts via advertisements, but after adopting the localisation marketing strategy, in localising/customising products, services and their advertisements, these latter could fit more the target client's demands. So by applying an advanced translation technique; which is called transcreation technique, as a process for the concentrated marketing strategy, at this stage, both translation and creation collaborate and conceive exclusive advertisements to the new targeted audience because direct translation may sometimes fail in doing the requested job. In other words, excelling the use of the local language, the understanding of the

local cultural traits and going under the consultation of the in-country laws and restrictions can make of the marketing strategy of dominating local markets abroad a soft power. It eventually becomes used on the target audience and on the favour of the foreign investors of local markets abroad.

2. Literature Review

The soft power, as came in Nye's concept, is a strategy that can be used in political, economical or cultural relations between the targeted people and the governor or the marketer....etc. it gently pushes the people to react in a desirable way or take decisions that are on the favour of the beneficiary. To reach this level of control/domination, the used strategy has to be very attractive, influential and persuasive.

Nye, on that, says: "Soft power rests on the ability to shape the preferences of others. [...] In behavioural terms, soft power is attractive power. In terms of resources, soft power resources are the assets that produce such attraction [...] such as an attractive personality, culture, political values, institutions, and policies that are seen as legitimate or having moral authority".⁷

It seems that the soft power concept in Nye's article has more than one single definition. The already cited definition was more on the theoretical/informative level, and the upcoming definition is more on the practical/descriptive level, where he again says that:

"By definition, soft power means getting others to want the same outcomes you want, and that requires an understanding of how they are hearing your messages and adapting them accordingly. It is crucial to understand the target audience [...] The ability to combine hard and soft power effectively is smart power".⁸

Therefore, when a fusion occurs between the soft and the hard power, it produces, according to Nye, a more effective power, because the outcomes of

this combination are more effective on regulating relations, and especially of the economical sector.

The target market, whether it is a domestic or a global market, has to go through a strategy of marketing. Doubtlessly, the strategies vary, due to the variations of patterns. Advertisement is a marketing tool that aims to transmit the message of the productive company to the targeted clients in a persuasive way. Since the patterns (language, demand, target clients, culture, political and economical regimes...etc) are different, exclusive advertisements had to be made in order to deliver the marketing message in a different way for each market.

Moreover, the STP: Segmentation, Targeting and Positioning, the holy trinity of marketing, as named by Schlegelmilch, is very crucial to the success of any business, where any disorganisation is likely to be very disadvantageous. For more in depth clarifications, Schlegelmilch sees that:

“Market segmentation aims to divide the market into smaller units [..., based on] geographic, demographic, psychographic, behavioral and benefit segmentation”

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These approaches are determiners. They show more focus on what to offer, who to serve, with what and how putting the product or the service in a position that they should be known as unique and never become confused with the available products or services in the market. In few words, these approaches are the division, the focus and the distinction.

Exclusive advertisement is a special message for commercial purposes. It is conceived particularly to the targeted audience of clients, where the customer feels him/herself being addressed directly. Marieke de Mooij, in her book, *Global Marketing and Advertising: Understanding Cultural Paradoxes*, sees that going global should not rely on standardisation strategies in providing products or conceiving advertisements, it should rather be focused more on the effectiveness of the cultural segmentation for effective marketing

communication strategies. She emphasises so clearly on the cultural aspects, where she says that:

“Advertising is more than words; it is made of culture [...] People process advertising messages in social and cultural contexts and then respond”.¹⁰

The cultural side in advertisements are mainly the conceptions of some daily life practices, or in the way the language is expressed, where the local thinking seems so obvious in such conceptions. So, even if the product, the service or the advertisement become standardised, their interpretations can only go relatively, and that is under their sociocultural perceptions. Values are determined by people, and their nature is just like the identity nature; distinctive and different. Therefore, there has to be careful considerations when introducing values in advertising conceptions because their interpretation should not be misunderstood by the targeted people. A successful advertisement is when values are used carefully.

Localisation, historically, updates to the early 1980's. It was mainly in the soft and hardware IT (Information Technology) industry, where the American companies aimed at having new markets. They first targeted Europe and later other countries. In the 1990's, it was much recommended as well for the gaming industry. Marketing strategies, that time, started acting global but thinking local because it was very important to the success of the global commercial campaign, where it did not opt for standardising products and services or advertisements. It rather made a lot of customisations to fit the new targeted market.

Budin sees that: “global stands for all the cross-cultural activities such as translation, localisation, but also customisation, etc”¹¹

To continue, it is especially transcreation. To know more about localisation or transcreation, let us first learn from some scholars, what localisation and transcreation really are. It seems that there is a remarkable confusion between many concepts in some scholar's definitions.

Budin thinks that: “Content localisation may very well involve more than translation in the traditional sense, i.e., we might have to re-create part of that content for another culture, or at least change fundamentally the way this content is presented to a certain culture”.¹²

It is obvious that this definition emphasises on the similarities between localisation and transcreation, and the common thing is in making changes in the original content. Schäler succeeded in clarifying the difference between localisation and translation by saying that: “Probably the most difficult distinction to make, however, is that between localisation and *translation*. Not just localisers, translators as well adapt products (text) linguistically and culturally so that they can be understood in different *locales*. However, translation does not necessarily deal with digital material whereas localisation is *always* happening in the digital world. This has a number of implications in a number of different areas”.¹³

So localisation is more in dealing with the customisation of products based on the criteria of the target local market, translation, on the other hand, deals more with products of linguistic nature such as texts of advertisements, menus, manuals...etc. But to be exact, direct translation does not offer such results, adaptation at some extent yes, but not direct translation. For this reason, a clarification should be added to Schäler’s definition, where the technique of translation that has an access in changing contents could be transcreation, and here we avoid falling again in confusions.

Schäler also says that: “According to the findings of a new market study undertaken by Word bank (2005) into the impact of language on the consumer’s purchasing behaviour, more than eight out of ten consumers expect global companies to sell to them in their own language and seven out of ten will not buy a product if they cannot understand the packaging”.¹⁴

So according to this statement, the global market is demanding changes and exclusivity in offers, since the demands are becoming unique. It focuses more on

the targeted client and does not impose the same adopted marketing strategy of the home market on the new local market.

Mangiron and O'Hagan, in their study of game localisation, see that localisation is one of the translation techniques that allow modifications in the original product so it gives the same experience to the gamers of the localised version. They think that:

“The brief of the localiser is to produce a version that will allow the players to experience the game as if it were originally developed in their own language and to provide enjoyment equivalent to that felt by the players of the original version. In order to achieve this it is crucial that the translators are familiar with the game domain”.¹⁵

The modifications are necessary for a version that should be transmitting the same experience sensations of the game. These modifications could be on the level of the language, the characters, the game itself ...etc. In the same context of modifications, they think that:

“Translators are often given *carte blanche* to modify, adapt, and remove any cultural references [...] Localisers are given the liberty of including new cultural references [...] This type of creative licence granted to game localisers would be the exception rather than the rule in any other types of translation. The technique of *compensation*, [...] domestication [...] adaptation [...] re-creation [...] all this gives a distinctive original flavour to the localised version [...] The traditional concept of fidelity to the original is discarded. In game localisation, transcreation, rather than just translation, takes place”.¹⁶

They also justified the use of all these techniques in order to create a different version that takes fidelity meaning into another path. So modifications are legitimate and the fidelity in translation is becoming advantageous to the target audience, and not to the original expression.

Transcreation is a type of translation. It is actually one of its free techniques that have the access in shaping a new form of the original content, based on the recommendations of the client or for the purpose of producing customised contents for fitting purposes to the target expression system. It is mainly a modeller of the content, when using the local language or the local thinking, with the incorporation of local sociocultural references. It is a sort of a soft power that has a huge impact on the target audience, and can make their response to the transcreated expression and the marketing purpose of the foreign investors of the local markets going hand in hand. Many scholars tried to provide a definition of transcreation technique, where others have just avoided that, because there are still maintainable confusions between transcreation and many other free translation techniques. Bernal-Merino thinks that:

“To some extent, this term shares similarities with other terms such as ‘domestication’, ‘localisation’, or ‘target-oriented translation’, as it implies a target-reader centred philosophy of translation”.¹⁷

So all these techniques share one thing so common between them all, it is in prioritising the reception of the target expression and not the original message. Geo-marketing is also focussing on the target audience, target expression and target culture in its strategy. It is where the soft power use appears.

This confusion did not stop Bernal-Merino from providing a definition where he says that:

“‘Transcreation’ might be a suitable term in the sense that it acknowledges unashamedly the fact of consciously replacing images, text and references that are deemed too culturally specific to be understandable or appealing for the target country. The end product is a translation that completely tilts the balance towards the target audience but claims to be the same product as the original, despite those differences”.¹⁸

So transcreation definition is saying it out loud in its creational part. It is then so obvious that modifications are taking place in the original expression because translating for the target audience can only transfer expressions that do not make the addresses feel the strangeness in the target content. Bernal-Merino continues with explaining the connection between the geo-marketing strategy in targeting niche markets and in the application of transcreation technique, where he says that:

“From CEOs’ point of view, they are maximising their investment in the form of one basic concept with slightly different selling strategies, depending on the local culture. It could be argued that companies translating commercials are in many cases recording new footage, therefore creating new advertisements, but this only seems to change the medium, from mono-channel text to multichannel film, not the translation task itself or the product being sold. It is the same basic principle that many companies have often applied to creating and selling cars, cosmetics, or burgers globally”.¹⁹

The strategy that transcreation follows is sort of a soft power that the local market investors use when they aim at winning more new local markets abroad because it is very effective in capturing the target audience’s attention. Transcreation makes changes in the content so that it sounds very original to the new addressee. Jakson sees that: “In addition to being an esthetic and creative procedure, transcreation is a constant project in progress, a voyage among world languages and literatures. Departing from a linguistic approach to expressive language”²⁰

The creativity part in transcreation makes of it influential, therefore, its application evolved from poems to advertisements. In addition to that, the unexpected encounters make of the transcreated version looks so original. And the originality is a significance of a creation that is addressed to its target audience.

Pool, J.²¹ tries, through his article: *Translators in a global community. The Translator as Mediator of Cultures*, to discuss a topic that turns out, at the end, to be as a wishful thinking of the idea of unifying one language and one culture to all people of the world. But translation, even at this level, still does its tasks and appears to be so valid in interpreting and translating in the same or between languages. Moreover, it is used in adapting contents of cultural references. So the idea of creating the expression of one common language and one common culture can only be formed thanks to the linguistic and the cultural expression rendition, that it is only possible under a translational process.

3. Methodology

This study was designed to follow a qualitative approach of research in order to demonstrate the soft power features that are manifested in the local language and the local sociocultural norms of the target audience. Because excelling the decryption of the target expression code system and using it as a marketing strategy can make the domination of the local market very easy.

The examined advertisement figures demonstrated how one productive company can vary its marketing strategy from one country into another by using the transcreation technique in translating its exclusive advertisements to each target community of clients. In other words, the addresser (the producer/the marketer) is one, but the addressees (clients in domestic and foreign markets) are numerous, therefore, to address them properly, there have to be multiple versions of communicating with them, and each version has to be identified as original on its own in the target expression system, because it is unique and it does not make sacred the source expression.

4. Results and Analysis

It is important to note that the following advertisements are examined for educational purposes only. No marketing or appropriation claiming intentions are held. Toyota, Nivea and L’Oreal were chosen in this research for their global marketing strategy, where transcreation technique is applied to conceive exclusive advertisements for different countries.

Toyota advertisement:

Figure 1: Toyota GR Supra Jarama Race track, Spain

Figure 2: Toyota GR Supra Jarama Racetrack, France

Figure 3: Toyota GR Supra Jarama Race track, UAE

Addresser	Toyota		
Product	Toyota GR Supra Jarama Race track Limited Edition		
Addresses	Spain	France	UAE

<p>Geo-marketing strategy: soft power use according to the need of the target market (in bold and italic).</p>	<p>Breaking stereotypes in: “Dicen que no podemos controlar nuestras emociones, nosotros te demostramos que sí. Descubre el nuevo #GRSupra Jarama Race track Limited Edition y déjate llevar. 🌟”</p>	<p>Solutions finder in : “Impossible de s’ennuyer sur la route des vacances à bord de la #GRSupra Jarama Race track Edition 😎”</p>	<p>Adopting contemporary norms (Woman Empowerment): “Go for it, do your best and drive like a girl”, says @amnalqubaisi_official encouraging younger girls to break down barriers and disrupt male dominated sports.</p> <p>”قَدِّمِي أفضل ما عندك وأظهري قدرتك على القيادة” تنصح أمانة القببسي الفتيات بكسر الحواجز والمشاركة في الرياضة التي يهيمن عليها الرجال”</p>
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Nivea advertisement

Figure4:Nivea Luminous 630 Antitaches, France

Figure 5: Nivea Luminous 630 Even Glow, Middle East

Figure6:Nivea Luminous 630 Anti manchas, Spain

Addresser	Nivea		
Product	Nivea Luminous630		
Addressees	France	Middle East	Spain
Geo-marketing strategy: soft power use according to the need of the target market (in bold and italic).	<p>Geographical considerations in : “Découvrez le nouveau duo Cellular Luminous630®, votre allié pour <i>diminuer les taches brunes</i> ! Son indice FPS 50 vous permettra <i>de profiter du soleil printanier</i> tout en protégeant votre peau.</p>	<p>Geographical considerations in: “NEW NIVEA LUMINOUS630 Even Glow <i>reduces dark spots</i> in 4 weeks!</p> <p>NIVEA مستحضر LUMINOUS630 Even Glow الجديد يخفف البقع الداكنة خلال 4 أسابيع فقط!</p>	<p>Geographical considerativos in: “¿Conoces la Crema de Día FP50 Luminous630 Fluido Triple Protección? Es <i>una fórmula anti manchas</i> de textura ligera que combina el ingrediente anti manchas</p>

	<p>#nivea #niveaestla #luminous630 #antitaches #bellepeau".</p>		<p>patentado LUMINOUS630 ® con un <i>alto factor de protección solar</i> (FP50), un paso fundamental a la hora <i>de reducir y prevenir las manchas</i> de tu piel y <i>conseguir una tez uniforme y luminosa</i>. ¿A qué estás esperando para probarla? ❤️ #NIVEAContigo"</p>
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L’Oreal advertisement

Figure 7: L’Oreal the brand, Australia

Figure 8: L’Oreal the brand, USA

Figure 9: L’Oreal the brand, Middle East

Addresser	L’Oreal		
Product	L’Oreal the brand		
Addressees	Australia	USA	Middle East
Geo-marketing strategy: soft power use according to the need of the target market (in bold and italic).	Identity as a beauty standard: “What is beauty? At L’Oréal, we believe that <i>beauty is a universal aspiration that transcends time, borders and cultures</i> 🤗. #Beauty gives us confidence	Beauty in inclusivity: “We believe that beauty begins when you are <i>free to be you, express yourself and love who you love.</i> 🏳️‍🌈 <i>L’Oréal supports the UN LGBTI Standards of Conduct for Business and stands for self-expression as a</i>	Beauty in diversity: “We asked you, what is beauty? For some beauty is a shape, a color, aesthetics... <i>At L’Oréal, we believe that beauty is a universal aspiration that transcends time, borders and cultures!</i> #Beauty gives us confidence in who we are and in who we want to be! Because we are creating the beauty that

	<p>in who we are, in who we want to be! Because we are creating the beauty that moves the world</p> <p>#beautythatmoves”</p>	<p>powerful driver for change and a path for inclusivity. #beautythatmoves”</p>	<p>moves the world #beautythatmoves</p> <p>سألنا ما هو الجمال؟ بالنسبة للبعض الجمال هو الشكل.. اللون.. الجماليات... نؤمن في لوريال بأن #الجمال هو الطموح اللامحدود الذي يتجاوز الزمن والحدود والثقافات حول العالم. فالجمال يمنحنا الثقة بأنفسنا وبما نطمح أن نكون! لأننا نقوم بإبداع جمال يحرك العالم #جمال يحرك العالم”</p>
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5. Discussion

The soft power strategy in geo-marketing is definitely an effective one because it takes each local market as a study case on its own and tries to use geo-aspects concepts that have the most effective and influential strategy on the local clients.

In Toyota’s strategy, the advertisement was conceived of verbal and non verbal expressions. Despite the same product, the images and the scripts were different for each country. In figure 1, for Spain’s advertisement, the image demonstrates the blue car GR SUPRA Jarama Racetrack in a garage. The script was a sort of a stereotype breaker, based on the local thinking, where the Spanish people have been known for their uncontrollable emotional excitement and the advertisement script tried to break this stereotype in “*Dicen que no podemos controlar nuestras emociones, nosotros te demostramos que sí.*”. In addition to that, there was also an expression of suspense for motivating the target client in order to try

the car in: “*Descubre el nuevo #GRSupra Jarama Racetrack Limited Edition y déjate llevar*”. It is eventually a transcreated advertisement that used different image and script according to the target expression system. In figure 2 for France’s advertisement, the image demonstrates the blue car GR Supra Jarama Racetrack on the road. The script was kind of a solution finder, where the focus was more on the speed of the car and the enjoyment of riding it during the long road when going on vacation in “*Impossible de s’ennuyer sur la route des vacances à bord de la #GRSupra Jarama Race track Edition.*”. In figure 3 for the UAE advertisement, the conception of the transcreated advertisement took the next level. The idea of adopting the changes and taking the challenges of the contemporary world were the context of the advertisement in “*Go for it, do your best and drive like a girl*”, says [@amnalqubaisi official](#) *encouraging younger girls to break down barriers and disrupt male dominated sports.*”. This phenomenon is very new for the Emirati girls and Toyota accepted and supported the challenge of empowering women.

In Nivea’s marketing strategy, the advertisement was also conceived of verbal and non verbal expressions. The images were also different. In figure 4, France illustrated with 5 images to show the process of applying the product. In figure 5 and 6, Middle East and Spain preferred using just one significant image that had all necessary visual demonstrations. Concerning the model, in France and Middle East advertisements, the dark spots were visible on her face then they disappeared after the use of the crème. In the advertisement of Spain, they showed just the final results of the crème; a clear face without dark spots.

Concerning the script, the geographical element was highly taken into consideration at this stage. In France’s advertisement, they referred to the sun as an enjoyable experience in “*Découvrez le nouveau duo Cellular Luminous630®, votre allié pour diminuer les taches brunes ! Son indice FPS 50 vous permettra de profiter du soleil printanier tout en protégeant votre*

peau.[#nivea](#) [#niveaestla](#) [#luminous630](#) [#antitaches](#) [#bellepeau](#).”.For Spain’s advertisement, it was more on the protection from the sun with the use of an incentive expression at the end in “¿Conoces la Crema de Día FP50 Luminous630 Fluido Triple Protección? Es una fórmula anti manchas de textura ligera que combina el ingrediente antimanchas patentado LUMINOUS630® *con un alto factor de protección solar* (FP50), un paso fundamental a la hora de reducir y prevenir las manchas de tu piel y conseguir una tez uniforme y luminosa. *¿A qué estás esperando para probarla?* [#NIVEAContigo](#).”.But in the Middle East, the sun element is not even mentioned because it is a blazing sun. They only focused on the protection from dark spots in “NEW NIVEA LUMINOUS630 Even Glow reduces dark spots in 4 weeks!.”.

In L’Oreal’s marketing strategy, the conception of verbal and non verbal expressions in the advertisements was distinctive. In figure 7 for Australia’s advertisements, the images demonstrated the concept of beauty by illustrating with people from different races and with different inclinations, and this is the identity of the Australian people. Regarding the script, it was harmonious with the non verbal content in “What is beauty? *At L’Oréal, we believe that beauty is a universal aspiration that transcends time, borders and cultures* 😊. [#Beauty](#) gives us confidence in who we are, in who we want to be! Because we are creating the beauty that moves the world 🌍 [#beautythatmoves](#)”. In figure 8, in both verbal and non verbal expressions, the USA advertisement preferred to be supportive to the LGBT community. In figure 9, for the Middle East advertisement, the part where LGBT was introduced in images or the script in the previous advertisements, was deleted for socio-cultural reasons. They instead selected the other images of the commercial campaign that expressed beauty through the diversity of races only.

To conclude, transcreation and localisation are both techniques that are used in the geo-marketing strategy. They put first every local aspect, from language, to

the way of thinking, to the culture, to the society norms...etc. These are actually the arsenal of the soft power use because when they are introduced in advertisements, they have a direct effect on the target client. As observed in the above studied advertisement figures, modifications or omissions were used to transcreate an exclusive advertisement for the target customers based on their local languages and local cultures.

6. Conclusion

The global market is a group of local markets that are geographically located in different territories. These local markets happen to be under different geo-economical regimes, geo-political rules and geo-cultural norms. To exercise an effective control/domination on these distinctive local markets, very smart and innovative marketing strategies are applied, such as localisation and transcreation in translating and re-creating exclusive advertisements to the target audience of the target market. The relation, of connecting the global market investor to the local market customer, is made under the connection of the identity representations of these two parts: producer and consumer. To reach such level of control, a good command of the local language or the local expression system, a deep knowledge of the local culture and specially its value and impact on the local people and an up-to-date consultation of the laws and restrictions of the target market and the country are all very necessary criterions to the process of commercialising abroad.

Reaching clients abroad goes under the same marketing strategy at home, but with very different procedures and measurements to take. The marketing strategy consists of studying the local language, the local culture, the local identity, the local client, the local market and the flexibility to the contemporary world commercialisation requirements...etc. The transcreator should be qualified to go under all these examinations and work in collaboration with the marketing staff and the advertisement teamwork, where all members have an important

role to play to guarantee the successful management on the target local market and every aspect that is related to it.

The communication skills are a soft power that gets exercised on the target community of clients without running to the use of force or unwillingness. The translator, on his/her turn, is the intermediate that uses the power of communication to reach the marketing goals, therefore, transcreators are hired to be the voice of the productive company. They seem to know how to talk to the addresses and know everything that is related to the way the communication should be held in its multimodal features. Another reason of them being trusted is that, they are aware of the subsequent data talk after transcreating advertisements.

Geo-culture and geopolitics identify the adopted geo-marketing strategy. It is obvious that the main element in common between the three approaches and the one that imposes these changes is the geographical factor. In other words, a place is not just a location, but a factor that gathers a certain group of people in a state, where specific norms, laws and rules are ruled, and they are eventually identified with. In other words, it is the framing of the bigger picture of the target community/market.

Notes

Figure 1:

https://www.instagram.com/p/CM1msrOD3pg/?utm_medium=copy_link&fbclid=IwAR0aSC6m3nbJbHEwqgp7Ag1ckwmra-C3HH0elzkNpY67-l-1OFm7ai6tUm8

Figure 2:

https://www.instagram.com/p/CSKBrnYiq2s/?utm_medium=copy_link&fbclid=IwAR1wNzCCn3exodxXSOUM_1IRCkaR7cMi6ycu0CvsJ7mUD6HP4QFuD7j9oCI

Figure 3:

https://www.instagram.com/p/CJA7hkagJHx/?fbclid=IwAR2NdyDYWYyVa-OIkODE8vubVd_zQT8eB0ucTZS6vpntnVlKwq1d93E5NFc

Figure 4:

https://www.instagram.com/p/CQjyqN6D1yL/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&fbclid=IwAR3lCeuBeAZZiHHiZLb7aFNqJaWb4C8yhkfBf5hvHoKeXVl06pszwqlFBIU

Figure 5:

https://www.instagram.com/p/CQqznelqoe/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&fbclid=IwAR1BfkmdgVqa_tFazJXrb6jiWV0mau4m7whpjyDaHjtPVDXG7QCok9DFqHE

Figure 6:

https://www.instagram.com/p/CRLwMrp1c5/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&fbclid=IwAR0Q5i4IBFrImbs7fsaz_fmjkONQeF8gILMDFXt8xpCvbbe0o8Q6JnZhiZ0

Figure 7:

<https://www.instagram.com/p/CNDMS9AsAMt/?fbclid=IwAR0kUp8PRAELBvLEtCedbQ8IoIONNax91S4knOn0sE33sG1oSs-pEkeUv9U>

Figure 8:

https://www.instagram.com/p/CRL_h1yl2ll/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&fbclid=IwAR3WsJeTRAAjMVgkInQYSyzQQFpeFgVOa81HNGWIbyKgyMEdpeZb4hSHts4

Figure 9:

https://www.instagram.com/p/CMKCM9rqitf/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&fbclid=IwAR1IepFRPo4Ia-EMG0zNAL5BiCnyQA6ylOtXwExcjforeWSwbCPrOue6Jzk

Endnotes

- [1] Rozov, N. S. (2012). "Geopolitics, Geoeconomics, and Geoculture: The Interrelation of Dynamic Spheres in the History of Russia." *Sociological Research* **51**(4): 67.
- [2] Schlegelmilch, B. B. (2022). Segmenting targeting and positioning in global markets. *Global marketing strategy*, Springer: 64.
- [3] Cowen, D. and N. Smith (2009). "After geopolitics? From the geopolitical social to geoeconomics." *Antipode* **41**(1): 23.
- [4] Cowen, D. and N. Smith (2009). "After geopolitics? From the geopolitical social to geoeconomics." *Antipode* **41**(1): 38.
- [5] Schlegelmilch, B. B. (2022). Segmenting targeting and positioning in global markets. *Global marketing strategy*, Springer: 73.
- [6] Winter, T. (2019). *Geocultural Power*, University of Chicago Press: 25.
- [7] Nye Jr, J. S. (2008). "Public diplomacy and soft power." *The annals of the American academy of political and social science* **616**(1): 95.
- [8] Nye Jr, J. S. (2008). "Public diplomacy and soft power." *The annals of the American academy of political and social science* **616**(1): 107.
- [9] Schlegelmilch, B. B. (2022). Segmenting targeting and positioning in global markets. *Global marketing strategy*, Springer: 63, 64.
- [10] De Mooij, M. (2021). *Global marketing and advertising: Understanding cultural paradoxes*, Sage: 45, 94.
- [11] Budin, G. (2008). "Global content management: challenges and opportunities for creating and using." *Topics in language resources for translation and localisation* **79**: 127.
- [12] Budin, G. (2008). "Global content management: challenges and opportunities for creating and using." *Topics in language resources for translation and localisation* **79**: 125.
- [13] Schäler, R. (2008). "Linguistic resources and localization." *Topics in language resources for translation and localisation*: 196.
- [14] Schäler, R. (2008). "Linguistic resources and localization." *Topics in language resources for translation and localisation*: 200.
- [15] Mangiron, C. and M. O'Hagan (2006). "Game Localisation: unleashing imagination with 'restricted' translation." *The Journal of Specialised Translation* **6**(1): 14, 15.

[16] Mangiron, C. and M. O'Hagan (2006). "Game Localisation: unleashing imagination with 'restricted' translation." *The Journal of Specialised Translation* 6(1): 16, 20.

[17] Bernal-Merino, M. Á. (2014). *Translation and localisation in video games: making entertainment software global*, Routledge: 88.

[18] Bernal-Merino, M. Á. (2014). *Translation and localisation in video games: making entertainment software global*, Routledge: 90.

[19] Bernal-Merino, M. Á. (2014). *Translation and localisation in video games: making entertainment software global*, Routledge: 91.

[20] Jackson, K. D. (2010). "Transcrição/transcreation: the Brazilian concrete poets and translation." *The Translator as Mediator of Cultures*: 144.

[21] Pool, J. (2010). "Translators in a global community." *The Translator as Mediator of Cultures* 3: 73.

References

Bernal-Merino, M. Á. (2014). *Translation and localisation in video games: making entertainment software global*, Routledge.

Budin, G. (2008). "Global content management: challenges and opportunities for creating and using." *Topics in language resources for translation and localisation* 79: 121-134.

Cowen, D. and N. Smith (2009). "After geopolitics? From the geopolitical social to geoeconomics." *Antipode* 41(1): 22-48.

De Mooij, M. (2021). *Global marketing and advertising: Understanding cultural paradoxes*, Sage.

Jackson, K. D. (2010). "Transcrição/transcreation: the Brazilian concrete poets and translation." *The Translator as Mediator of Cultures*: 139-160.

Mangiron, C. and M. O'Hagan (2006). "Game Localisation: unleashing imagination with 'restricted' translation." *The Journal of Specialised Translation* 6(1): 10-21.

Nye Jr, J. S. (2008). "Public diplomacy and soft power." *The annals of the American academy of political and social science* 616(1): 94-109.

Pool, J. (2010). "Translators in a global community." *The Translator as Mediator of Cultures* 3: 73.

Rozov, N. S. (2012). "Geopolitics, Geoeconomics, and Geoculture: The Interrelation of Dynamic Spheres in the History of Russia." *Sociological Research* 51(4): 67-90.

Schäler, R. (2008). "Linguistic resources and localization." *Topics in language resources for translation and localisation*: 195-214.

Schlegelmilch, B. B. (2022). Segmenting targeting and positioning in global markets. *Global marketing strategy*, Springer: 129-159.

Winter, T. (2019). *Geocultural Power*, University of Chicago Press.